

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

**Deliverable 2.7 Practitioners’ gaps
and requirements – 1st public
available annual report for industry
and academia**

Public

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1. Summary

This document contains the 3 publicly available reports developed from CYCLOPES practitioner workshops. These reports outline the priorities of Law Enforcement at an operational level, and the opportunities for development across the three topics covered by the workshops:

- Digital Forensics on Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies – organised on 15th December 2021;
- Cybercrime relating to Remote Desktop Protocols and similar technologies - organised on 10th - 11th February 2022;
- Social Engineering to enable Cybercrime - organised on 30th – 31st March 2022.

Representatives of European Law Enforcement Agencies participated in each of the workshop. These reports are intended to act as a steer for industry and academia.

2. Methodology for workshops' topic selection

Methodology in first project's year

According to the WP2 methodology, described in D2.1, first 3 topics for practitioner's workshops were discussed and chosen with domain leaders (Swedish Police, Polish Police, ZITiS) and Home Office.

Methodology for next project years

Based on the questionnaire, most common gaps and priorities were identified. The questionar was circulated to consortium members, CYCLOPES network of practitioners (not consortium members) wider project partners (e.g. Europol, EJCEN, EC). The results were analysed and a proposal for next three Practitioner Workshops was developed based on the most selected priority topics. This proposal was put to the CYCLOPES Work Package Leaders and Practitioner Group Leaders, and a consensus is reached on the topics selected.

The workshops are ordered such that the most suitable workshops for Joint Live Exercises (JLEs) take place before the end of the calendar year, to allow sufficient time for JLE preparations.

This methodology is consistently reviewed and refined, with the lessons learned being incorporated into new questionnaires and stakeholder engagement processes.

3. Digital Forensics on Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies

Digital Forensics is the examination and analysis of data collected from electronic devices. In the last decade – with the invention and distribution of smartphones, and the uptake of wearable technologies such as smart watches – this has become a common and invaluable evidence type for law enforcement agencies (LEAs) during investigations.

The volume and diversity of data stored and available on these devices has risen steeply alongside their popularity, capturing a vast array of user information including location data, health data and financial transactions. With this growth in data collection and device usage, companies have had to focus more on the security of this data and enhance protection of the device against malicious attacks. This however has increased technical barriers and complications for LEAs.

The *Digital Forensics on Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies* workshop brought together expert practitioners from across 13 European countries to explore LEA operational use and future requirements for digital forensics on Mobile Devices and Wearables.

3.1. Priorities of Law Enforcement in the field of Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies

The main priorities for Law Enforcement raised by practitioners focused on the need for improved technical solutions to combating encryption and tools to automate labour-intensive tasks such as the extraction and analysis of data from mobile phones. Additionally, tools to help gain access to a suspect's Cloud storage would aid investigations. Practitioners also stated that the current training offer is insufficient and to keep up with the constant, fast-paced evolution of mobile technologies and wearable devices, they are having to perform continual self-directed study to relearn how to gain access to devices.

3.2. Opportunities for development within Digital Forensics on Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies

- **Tools to bypass passwords and encryption**

More powerful tools for bypassing passwords and encryption of devices and communication platforms.

- **Integrated tools for data extraction, analysis and visualisation**

Integrated automated tools that are capable of extracting, analysing and categorising data, which can function with several different devices.

- **Improved digital forensics training offer**

Bespoke hands-on training packages for specialist officers that is regular, low-cost and covers data preservation, forensic tools and software with regular updates and training on new mobile and wearable technologies being introduced to consumers. Additionally basic training packages made widely available to frontline officers, the judiciary and law makers.

- **Data storage solutions**

Technical solutions to store the wide array of extracted digital forensic data, with integrated AI/machine learning to help search, categorise and analyse this data.

- **A framework to coordinate and encourage engagement from ISPs, device manufactures and software providers with investigations**

A framework for a coordinated Law Enforcement approach to engaging ISPs in a timely manner, potentially supported by legislation to compel product and service providers to cooperate.

4. Cybercrime relating to Remote Desktop Protocol and other similar technologies

Usage of Remote Desktop Protocol (RDP)-enabled technologies that allow people to remotely access their workspaces has significantly increased following the COVID-19 pandemic. Cybercriminals took notice of this trend and are taking advantage of the opportunities to exploit weaknesses in both personal and business systems.

Criminals utilise social engineering or technical means to install clients using RDP on a victim's system. They employ a range of available commercial clients and self-made or underground software called RATs (Remote Access Trojans). These provide a backdoor into the victim machine and can allow the criminal unfettered access, including the ability to steal sensitive data.

Crimes relating to RDP have a huge number of victims and significant societal impact. Combatting this crime domain is of high priority for Law Enforcement.

The *Cybercrime relating to RDP and other similar technologies* workshop brought together expert practitioners from across 8 European countries to explore how LEAs experience cybercrime involving RDP at a working level and to discuss LEA priorities to better investigate and disrupt this crime domain.

4.1. Priorities of Law Enforcement in the field of Cybercrime relating to RDP

Practitioners indicated that introducing and improving frameworks, processes and platforms that enable cross-border collaboration is a key priority area for the Law Enforcement community. In addition, practitioners highlighted the priorities of developing improved tools for first responders; improving public and organisational RDP awareness; improving Law Enforcement specialist provision by offering more opportunities for upskilling and specialist career progression; strengthening regulation of VPNs and other service providers.

4.2. Opportunities for development within Remote Desktop Protocol and other similar technologies

- **Framework for international accountability**

RDP attacks and cybercrime in general is an increasingly transnational crime domain; the infrastructure utilised to carry out RDP attacks is often hosted abroad and routed through several different countries. Practitioners highlighted an urgent need to develop a framework for international accountability, and legislation to allow LEAs to pursue criminals abroad.

- **International agreements for cross-LEA data sharing**

International agreements on what information LEAs are able and willing to share and international standards for digital evidence. It would also be useful to publish a document outlining log file data retention times for different countries.

- **Platform for cross-border information and intelligence sharing**

A secure, automated, real-time platform that facilitates cross-border information and intelligence sharing relating to RDP enabled cyber-attacks. This should have functionality to share net flow data; share intelligence on active cybercriminal groups and current scams; share tools and best practice.

- **Regulation of ISPs, VPNs and RDP service providers**

Legal standards for service provision, including the collection of user registration data and the recording of standardised log data. In addition, a framework for questioning service providers about historical RDP breaches and legislation to compel service providers to share log data with LEAs.

- **First responder tools**

User-friendly tools with functionality for automated RDP data extraction and timelining, preservation of volatile data, and integrated software for bypassing and bruteforcing passwords.

- **Systems architecture directory**

A directory that outlines what log files are generated and where they are located for different systems, companies, and service providers.

5. Social Engineering to enable Cybercrime

Although most cybercrime will result in a technical exploitation of a computer or a network, the most common route into a victim's system is through Social Engineering. Advances in cyber security are hardening networks to make 'Brute Force' attacks far more difficult, and with end-to-end encryption becoming the default for most communications, social engineering gives the criminal the greatest opportunity for system compromise.

In this context, Social Engineering refers to the range of techniques employed by cybercriminals to exploit human nature in order to defraud. These utilise a vast range of vectors from mass directed email (phishing) or SMS (smishing) campaigns to attacks on specific high-

value targets (spear-phishing). Social Engineering-enabled cybercrime has huge financial and security impacts across the general public, as well as the public and private sector. It is significant area of concern and priority for Law Enforcement.

The *Social Engineering to enable Cybercrime* workshop brought together expert practitioners from across 8 European countries to explore how LEAs experience cybercrime involving Social Engineering at a working level and to discuss LEA priorities to better investigate and disrupt this crime domain.

5.1. Priorities of Law Enforcement in the field of Social Engineering

The main priorities of the Law Enforcement community centre on improving awareness and understanding of Social Engineering-enabled cybercrime across first responders, the judiciary, and the general public; improving processes and structures that enable cross-border collaboration, particularly beyond Europe; developing improved accessible tools for financial investigations looking at cryptocurrencies and dark markets; developing improved tools to automate time and resource intensive tasks.

5.2. Opportunities for development within Social Engineering

- **Cybercrime clustering platform**

A tool that provides automated linking of cybercrimes by Modus Operandum (MO). This tool would include standardised identifiers for MO and an AI-enabled platform to cross-reference these identifiers with other data (e.g. IP data) and cluster crimes which are likely to have the same perpetrator.

- **Targeted training offer for first responders and for members of the Judiciary**

A targeted training package and manual for complaint receivers on cybercrime basics, procedures for digital evidence gathering and handling, cryptocurrency investigations and cybercrime reporting and triage. Improved training for judges and prosecutors to understand and present digital evidence in way that is accessible to a jury.

- **Cryptocurrency tracing tools**

Price-competitive tools to track cryptocurrency transactions, including through cryptocurrency mixers, that can provide data that is admissible in court.

- **Dark market scaping tools**

An EU level tool for scraping dark markets along with a platform to which practitioners could submit search terms or onion links for automated searching and cross-referencing with investigations.

- **Improved log analysis and data visualisation tools**

Automated tools to analyse and visualise the vast amounts of digital data generated in investigations. These tools must be transparent in their working and the officers operating the tools must understand how they work, to ensure the evidence they generate can be admissible in court.

- **A framework to update existing legislation with cybercrime-related considerations**

A framework to facilitate adjusting existing legislation to take cyber-considerations into account could provide a more efficient approach to helping legislation keep pace with technological advances than introducing entirely new cyber legislation.

6. CYCLOPES Workshop Lessons Learned

Positives:

- Fantastic engagement with 60+ practitioners over 16 countries providing a great level of detail surrounding LEA capability gaps and practitioner priorities across the three workshop topics. These have been exploited by other Work Packages within the project who are looking towards the solutions space.
- Consistent positive practitioner feedback – practitioners feel comfortable and that their contributions to workshops are valued.
- Development of the CYCLOPES network and informal practitioner to practitioner networks supporting cross-LEA and cross-jurisdiction informal support.

Areas needed improvements:

- Workshops were conducted remotely via Microsoft Teams; hybrid – blended between in attendance person and via Microsoft Teams; and exclusively face-to-face. Practitioner feedback and facilitators agreed that face-to-face workshops proved by far the most productive option. It is planned that future workshops will only be hosted on a face-to-face basis.
- Timing was consistently noted as an issue by practitioners, who expressed frustrations that discussions had to be cut short. Therefore preworkshop process were adapted to gather more information from practitioners before the workshops. This allows to undertake more preworkshop analysis to make better use of limited time and to capture more detailed information.
- To encourage more rich discussions, more Work Packages and wider project partners have been invited to workshops; including a prosecutor's perspective through the EJC has proved particularly useful to ground discussions on legislative challenges.

- We should use the opportunity of meetings with LEA practitioners to disseminate during the workshop information about what EUROPOL (EC3, EIL), CEPOL, ECTEG, EACTDA, EJCN and other, already offer to practitioners fighting cybercrime.

7. Exploitation of Workshops Results

Workshops Output Reports are compiled and shared within the CYCLOPES consortium following each workshop. Work Package 3 identifies solutions to the technical requirements identified in workshops. Likewise, Work Package 4 identifies areas for standardisation and Work Package 7 looks at legal and ethical issues and solutions. WP5 is responsible for sharing project outcomes with relevant stakeholders, therefore reports are already shared with ECTEG, EC3, EUROPOL Innovation Lab, EJCN, ENLETS, EMPACT Cybercrime Driver, EuCB, DG HOME. CEPOL is one of the stakeholders which will be included in agencies receiving project outcomes.

Public Available reports are also produced from each workshop to provide a steer to industry and academia surrounding LEA priorities across the cybercrime domains covered in the workshops.

Other Work Packages drive engagement with the CYCLOPES network via social media channels, webinars, email correspondence and attendance of industry events (conferences etc).